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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in our contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

ANALYSIS OF LICENSING AND OPERATIONS OF BANKS UNDER THE BANKS AND OTHER FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS ACT (BOFI ACT) 2020

By

Ahmad Sadisu Abdulmumin¹

Abstract

The Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act BOFIA 2020 provide a revised regulatory regime for banks and other financial institutions. Undoubtedly, the Banks play a key role in the economic growth of the country and is therefore one of the most heavily regulated industries in Nigeria. This is in order to ensure that the banking industry remains reliable and capable of driving efficiency in economic activities. To regulate the banking industry, it is mandatory to obtain licence before any person or entity commences banking business in Nigeria. This study aimed to analyze Chapter A, Part One of the BOFIA 2020. In so doing, the study highlighted the practical steps and procedures for acquiring banking licence, the authority responsible for the grant or issuance of license and revocation of banking license. The study also discusses operations of banks including opening and closing of branches, operation of foreign banks, capital requirements etc. as contained in the BOFIA 2020. The study employed the doctrinal method of research wherein data from primary source including the BOFIA 2020, decided cases as well as secondary sources in the form of journals, books, e-books, websites etc. were obtained. The finding of the study indicates that, the BOFIA 2020 has brought progressive innovations in the Nigerian banking industry. However, the challenges existing within the industry and those necessitated by the BOFIA 2020 remains a bottleneck thereby leading to certain hardship and as such, making the Act especially the requirements for granting licence uneasy to be complied with. The study therefore recommends among others, the need for review of the Act so as ameliorate the hardship in obtaining a banking license.

KEYWORDS: Banks, Financial Institution, License, Banking Operations

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1.0 Introduction

The importance of the banking industry in a society cannot be far-fetched; it is the artery through which economic life blood of the nation runs. The Nigerian banking industry plays a key role in the economic growth of the country and is therefore one of the most heavily regulated industries in Nigeria². Taking into account the importance of the business of banking, Nigeria has made several legislations in order to accommodate the changes as well as the challenges that might affect the smooth running of the banking industry. The 1952 Banking Ordinance was the very first legislation which introduced some regulations into banking.³ By 1958, another Banking Ordinance was passed into law repealing the 1952 Ordinance. Subsequently, banking legislations prescribed rules, regulations and principles which must be observed by any entity willing to partake in banking business. These legislations further imposes duties and obligations on licensed banks and equally put in place set of rules and guidelines empowering the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and other related bodies like the Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) to supervise and control banking institutions so as to ensure smooth running of the business and to instill confidence in the banks from members of the public.⁴

The objective of this research is to make an analysis of licensing and operations of banks as provided for under Chapter A, Part One of the BOFIA 2020- the latest Act that regulates banking and other related institutions in Nigeria. The BOFIA 2020 provides for an exposition on the steps in acquiring the license to operate a bank in Nigeria, the documents required for this purpose, as well as the instances where such licenses may be revoked by the issuing authority. Undoubtedly, the BOFIA 2020 seeks to provide a suitable, contemporaneously relevant legal framework for banking

²Ibrahim Alley, 'BOFIA 2020 and Financial System Stability in Nigeria: Implications for Stakeholders in the African Largest Economy' *Journal of Banking Regulation* (2023) 24:184–205 <<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41261-022-00192-6>> accessed on 28 November, 2023

³ Adedoyin Soyibo and Femi Adekanye, *The Nigerian Banking System In the Context of Policies of Financial Regulation and Deregulation*, African Economic Research Consortium, Nairobi December 1992 <<https://aercafrica.org/old-website/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/RP17.pdf>> accessed 18th July 2025.

⁴Ibid

activities in Nigeria.⁵ The Act prohibits the carrying on of such businesses in Nigeria except under license and by a company incorporated in Nigeria.⁶

The BOFIA 2020 was signed into law on the 13th day of November 2020, repealing the hitherto existing principal banking legislation enacted in 1991 and 2004 respectively. It provides a revised legal regime for the Nigerian banking industry. Based on the provisions of BOFIA 2020, all business combinations involving banks in Nigeria are now primarily supervised and approved by the CBN.⁷

2.0 Banking Licence

To have a better understanding of what a banking license is, it will be important to define the words separately, “Banking” and “licence”. On the first hand, banking is defined as:

the business of receiving deposit on the current account, savings account or other similar accounts, paying or collecting cheques drawn by or paid in by customers, provision of finance consultancy and advisory services relating to corporate and investment matters, making or managing investment on behalf of any person whether such business are conducted digitally, virtually or electronically on or such other business as the governor may, by order published in the gazette, designated as banking business⁸.

Licence on the other hand, is a legal right to do something you wouldn't normally be allowed to do. It may also mean a document that shows permission has been given to do, own, or use something.⁹ In the legal context, a licence is defined as grant of

⁵ Ibrahim Alley, 'BOFIA 2020 and Financial System Stability in Nigeria: Implications for Stakeholders in the African Largest Economy' *Journal of Banking Regulation* (2023) 24:184–205 <<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41261-022-00192-6>> accessed on 28 November, 2023

⁶ *ibid*

⁷ Ugochukwu Mbakogu and Oluwatitoni Oyefeso, *A Review of the BOFIA 2020 – Effects on Nigeria's Fintech Ecosystem*, Africa Law Practice NG & Company <<https://www.alp.company/sites/default/files/ALP%20-%20A%20REVIEW%20OF%20THE%20BANKS%20AND%20OTHER%20FINANCIAL%20INSTITUTIONS%20ACT%202020%20%E2%80%93%20EFFECTS%20ON%20NIGERIA%E2%80%99S%20FINTECH%20ECOSYSTEM%20.pdf>>

⁸ S. 131 BOFIA 2020

⁹ Cambridge Online Dictionary, accessed from <<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/capital-ratio>> on 23 February 2025.

authority or permission to engage in a specific activity, issued by a government agency or other authorized entity. It is a revocable privilege rather than a guaranteed right.¹⁰ Simply put, banking licence is an official document or permit issued by the CBN that grants legal permission for a financial institution to conduct banking business in Nigeria¹¹. The banking licence specifies the scope and activities the bank is authorized to undertake, such as taking deposits, providing loans, foreign exchange service. Etc. The banking license is considered an intangible asset for the bank as it grants protective legal rights and the liability to operate in a regulated financial sector¹².

2.1. Application for Grant of Licence

Applying for a banking licence involves crossing certain hurdles which every applicant must cross before the grant of a banking license. The first hurdle is incorporation. The BOFIA 2020 specifically provides that no person shall carry on any banking business in Nigeria except it is duly incorporated in Nigeria and holds a valid banking licence from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN).¹³ The Act further provides that, any person who contravenes this provision and carries on banking business without first obtaining licence commits an offence and is liable upon conviction to a prison time for a term of not less than five years or a fine of not less than N50,000,000 or two times the cumulative deposits or other amount collected or both imprisonment and fine.¹⁴

The procedure for the grant of license is to make a written application to the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria for grant of licence.¹⁵ Upon submission of the application containing all such information, documents and reports as required by the CBN, the shareholders of the proposed bank shall deposit with the CBN certain sum equal to the minimum to the paid-up share capital.¹⁶ Meanwhile, the governor may

¹⁰ *ibid*

¹¹ Adeola Oyinlade & Co, Types Of Banking License And Requirement for Grant Of a Bank Operation License In Nigeria <https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/financial_services/1512322> accessed on 17th July 2025

¹² *ibid*

¹³S. 2 (1) BOFIA 2020

¹⁴ S. 2 (2) BOFIA2020

¹⁵ S. 3 (1) (a)(b)(c)(d)(e)(f) BOFIA 2020

¹⁶S. 3(2) BOFIA 2020

grant the application with or without conditions or may refuse to grant the licence, and the governor need not give any reason for such refusal.¹⁷

It is important to point out here that the governor of the Central Bank reserves the right to vary, revoke or impose fresh or additional conditions on a licence. However, before he does so, he must give notice to the bank concerned and must equally give the bank the opportunity to make representation to him.¹⁸ Any bank which fails to comply with any fresh or additional condition imposed in relation to its licence, shall be liable to a penalty of not less than N5,000,000 and an additional fine of N100,000 for each day during which the fresh or additional condition is not complied with.¹⁹

In applying for a banking license, the BOFIA 2020 makes a couple of changes to the list of things required to accompany the application. For example, it now requires a feasibility report for the proposed bank License including financial projection of up to five (5) years. To have a better understanding of the requirements and procedure, it is important we examine the stages in applying for a banking licence, namely:

- a. Grant of approval in principle.
- b. Grant of a final licence.
- c. Pre-commencement of operation requirements.

a. Grant of Approval in Principle (AIP)

Here, a formal application for the grant of a licence to carry on the business of banking is made in writing to the Governor of the CBN by the promoters of the prospective bank attaching the following²⁰:

- (i) Non-refundable application fee of N500, 000.00,
- (ii) Deposit of minimum capital of N 25 billion with Central Bank of Nigeria on application with evidence of deposit by each shareholder. The source of capital contribution by each shareholder/ subscriber would subsequently be verified by Bank Examiners,
- (iii) Feasibility Report/Business Plan. This report should contain information on the following; Minimum paid-up capital requirement of N25 billion for

¹⁷ibid

¹⁸S. 5 (4) BOFIA 2020

¹⁹S. 5 (5) BOFIA 2020

²⁰S. 3 (1) BOFIA 2020

new banking licence; Ownership structure in columnar format showing name of proposed investor(s); profession/business and percentage shareholding. Detailed bio-data/resume of shareholders should be attached; Objectives of the bank; Services to be rendered; Branch expansion programme; Organizational structure showing functional units and reporting relationships and grade (status) of heads of departments/units; Staff Training Programme; I.T. Programme requirements/facilities; Five (5) year financial projection. The assumptions underlying the projections must be stated; Board composition should not be unwieldy (10-20 directors); Roles and responsibilities of the Board & its subcommittees must be spelt out in the business plan; Criteria for selecting board members should be stated in Business Plan. This must be proportional to shareholding; List of proposed directors and their detailed resume should be attached and submitted; List of identified senior management staff (AGM and above) and detailed curriculum vitae stating their qualification and experience, track records etc. should be submitted; Internal Controls, such as delegation of functions, running of the bank (i.e. at least two officers to be involved in all major decisions); Succession plan for key officers and Corporate planning.

- (iv) A draft copy of the Memorandum and Articles of Association (MEMART) of the proposed bank. Relevant issues to be addressed in the draft MEMART include, but are NOT limited to: Name of proposed bank, Object clauses, Subscribers to the MEMART, Procedure for amendment, Procedure for share transfer/disposal, Appointment of directors. In the case of a non-interest bank, a list of experts on non-interest banking or finance that will serve as its advisory committee of experts and such other information, documents and reports as the CBN may specify. These may include: Shareholders Agreement providing for Disposal/transfer of shares as well as authorization, amendments, waivers, reimbursement of expenses etc, Statement of intent to invest in the bank, Technical Services Agreement (where applicable).

Following the receipt of an application with complete and satisfactory documentation, the CBN shall communicate its decision to the applicant within 90 days. Where the CBN is satisfied with the application, it shall issue an Approval-in-Principle (AIP) to

the applicant. Note however, the proposed bank shall not incorporate its name with the CAC until an AIP has been obtained.²¹

b. Grant of Final Banking Licence

This application is made not later than six (6) months after the grant of A.I.P, the promoters of a proposed bank must submit application for the grant of a final banking licence to the governor with following documents²²:

- (i) Non-refundable licensing fee of N2, 000,000 (Two Million Naira Only) in bank draft payable to CBN.
- (ii) 3 certified true copies of Certificate of Incorporation of the Bank, Memorandum and Articles of Association, Form CAC 2 (Allotment of shares) and Form CAC 7 (Particulars of Directors) of the Bank.
- (iii) Evidence of location of Head Office/Branch Building (rented or owned) for the take-off of banking business.
- (iv) Changes (if any) in the Board, Management and Shareholding should be clearly stated for necessary appraisal.
- (v) Evidence of strong room, loading bay and Banking Hall Facilities.
- (vi) Bullion Lorries with necessary security gadgets.
- (vii) Evidence of installation I.T. facilities/computerization.
- (viii) Copies of letters of offer and acceptance of employment in respect of the Management Team.

As a requirement to grant the final licence, the CBN will conduct an inspection of the premises and facilities of the proposed bank to check the physical structure of the office building and infrastructure provided for the take-off, check the originals of the documents submitted for sighting, meet with the board and management team whose

²¹ See the CBN Guidelines For Licensing and Regulation of Payment Service Banks, 2020 accessed from <<https://www.cbn.gov.ng>> on the 17th July 2025; O. M Atoyebi, "The Procedure for the Acquisition of a Bank Operation License In Nigeria And The Revocation Of Licenses, accessed from <https://omaplex.com.ng/the-procedure-for-the-acquisition-of-a-bank-operation-licence-in-nigeria-and-the-revocation-of-licences/>-on 17th July 2025.

²² Ibid

Resumes had been submitted earlier, verify the capital contributions of the promoters, verify the integration of its infrastructure with the National Payment Systems²³.

c. Pre-commencement of operation requirements.

After a final licence has been granted and before the proposed bank commences business, it will submit the following documents through a letter, informing CBN of its readiness to begin operation;

- i. Copy of Shareholders register;
- ii. Copy of share certificate issued to each investor;
- iii. Draft copy of the opening statement of affairs signed by the directors and auditors; Evidence of insurance coverage and the insurance policies; Enterprise Risk Management Framework (ERMF);
- iv. Internal control policy;
- v. Minutes of pre-commencement board meeting;
- vi. Evidence of integration of the bank's infrastructure with the National Payment System.²⁴

2.2. Issuance of Banking Licence

A banking licence is issued by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and authorizing a company duly incorporated in Nigeria to carry out banking business in the country. As stated, application for grant of banking licence is made to the governor of the CBN in writing; the governor after examination of a company's application may issue or refuse to issue licence and need not give any reason for its refusal.

Ordinarily, the CBN Governor may with the approval of the Board of Directors grant licence to a bank either based on condition or otherwise after a careful examination of the application. Alternatively, he reserves the absolute power to refuse the grant of licence even where all criteria were met for the grant of a licence without giving any reason whatsoever.²⁵

2.3. Revocation of Licence

²³ See the CBN Guidelines For Licensing and Regulation of Payment Service Banks, 2020 accessed from <<https://www.cbn.gov.ng>> on the 17th July 2025

²⁴ *ibid*

²⁵ S. 3 (2) BOFIA 2020

The Governor of the CBN, with the approval of the Board, and a notice published in the Federal Government Gazette or print and electronic media, can revoke a licence to operate a bank in Nigeria under specified situations if it is satisfied that the bank:

- (a) Ceases to carry on the type of banking business for which it was licenced to carry on for any continuous period of six months, or any period aggregating six months during a continuous period of twelve months in Nigeria;
- (b) Goes into liquidation;
- (c) Fails to comply with any condition subject to which the licence was granted;
- (d) Has insufficient assets to meet its liabilities;
- (e) Conducts its business in an unsound manner or its directors engage in unsafe practice;
- (f) Is involved in a situation, circumstance, action or inaction which constitutes a threat to financial stability;
- (g) Fails to comply with any obligation imposed upon it by or under the BOFIA, or the Central Bank of Nigeria Act, or any other rule, regulation, guideline or directive made;
- (h) in the opinion of the Central Bank of Nigeria, is critically undercapitalized with a capital adequacy ratio below the prudential minimum or such other ratio as the CBN may prescribe;
- (i) Fails to commence banking operation within 12 months after the grant of a licence;
- (j) Fails to comply with the provision of sections 9 and 13 of the BOFIA.²⁶

In the same vein, Section 9(1) of the Act provides that the Bank shall determine the minimum paid-up capital requirement of each category of banks licensed under the Act which shall be complied with by each bank within the time prescribed by the Bank. Failure to comply with the provision within such period as prescribed by the CBN is a ground for the revocation of any license issued under this Act repealed by it.²⁷ The CBN Governor has the power to revoke any license where a bank found critically

²⁶S.12 (1) BOFIA 2020

²⁷ S. 9 (2) BOFIA 2020

undercapitalized with a capital adequacy ratio below the prudential minimum or such other ratio as the CBN may prescribe.²⁸

On grounds of public Interest, the Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) 2020 empower the CBN to take actions, including revocation of licenses, in cases where a bank's operations are deemed detrimental to public confidence in the financial system. Section 12(f) of BOFIA provides that the Governor may revoke any license granted under this Act if a bank is involved in a situation, circumstance, action or inaction which constitutes a threat to financial stability.

3.0 Operation of Banks

Operation of banks entails specific activities, practices and procedure which the banks are lawfully permitted to conduct. Banks in Nigeria operates what is known as the "branch banking system." It is the commonest banking system. Under this system, a big bank has a number of branches in different parts of the country and even many branches within a cosmopolitan city. For instance, the Central Bank of Nigeria being the apex bank has other branches in all states of the nation and such is the case with other banks.²⁹

The Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act, 2020 clearly highlights in specific sections the general operations of a bank to include:

(a) Opening and Closing of Branches

The Act unequivocally provides thus: "No bank shall open or close any branch office, cash centre, and representative office anywhere within or outside Nigeria except with the prior written consent of the Bank"³⁰ It has been stated above as part of the requirement for the grant of a final banking licence, an applicant must show evidence of location of Head Office or Branch Building (rented or owned) for the take-off of banking business. Suffice to say that a bank which has been granted licence to operate a banking business and which seeks to open or close its branch office, cash centre or representative office either in Nigeria or abroad must secure the permission of the

²⁸ S. (12) (h) BOFIA 2020

²⁹ Abdullahi S. Araga and Temi Olajide Arise, 'Banking Methods and Process' (a lecture Material for students of National Open University of Nigeria NOUN) pg. 65 <<https://nou.edu.ng/coursewarecontent/BFN308.pdf>> accessed on 17th July 2025.

³⁰S. 6(1) BOFIA 2020

CBN before doing so. This, the bank will do by giving a notice in writing to the governor of the CBN of its intention to so open or close as the case may be. The notice of intention must be presented at least six months before the date of the closure or within shorter period as the governor may allow.³¹

In a circumstance where a bank open or close any branch office, cash centre, representative office or any other banking outlet without notice, the governor may either order the closure of the bank branch office, cash centre, representative office or any other banking outlet which is opened without the prior consent of the CBN or rather make an order re-opening of the branch office, cash center, representative office or any other banking outlet which is closed without the prior consent of the CBN.³²

The Act went further to impose penalty of N5, 000,000 and 100,000 (additional penalty for each day during which the contravention continues) against any banks which fails to comply with the above provisions.³³

(b) Restructuring, Reorganization, Merger and Disposal, etc. of Banks.

The Act prohibits banks to make any form of corporate restructuring in the form of sale, disposal or transfer, merger etc., which may result in transferring a significant shareholding in a bank except with the prior consent of the CBN Governor. The Act states thus: "Except the prior consent of Governor, no bank shall enter into an agreement or arrangement which results in change in the control of bank, or the transfer of a significant shareholding in the bank, for the sale, disposal or transfer of the whole or any part of the business of the bank, for the amalgamation or merger of the bank with any other person, for the restructuring, reconstruction, re-organisation of the bank, or to transfer the whole or any part of the business of the bank to any agent."³⁴

Penalty is imposed against any bank for failing to duly obtain the consent of the CBN Governor before engaging in any restructuring, reorganisation, merger, etc. of banks. The defaulting bank shall pay a fine of not less than N20, 000,000 and in the case of

³¹S. 6(2) BOFIA 2020

³²S. 6 (5) BOFIA 2020

³³S. 6 (4) BOFIA 2020

³⁴S. 7 (1) BOFIA 2020

a continuing breach, to an additional penalty of N500, 000 for each day during which the breach continues.³⁵

The Act further provides that any restructuring, reorganisation, merger, etc. carried out without the consent of the Governor shall be void and any transfer of interest there under shall be ineffectual except where such transaction is subsequently ratified in writing by the CBN.³⁶

(c) Minimum paid-up share capital of banks

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) determines the minimum paid-up share capital for each category of banks that are licenced under the BOFI Act, and the banks must comply with this particular provision within the time prescribed by the CBN.³⁷ Failure by the banks to comply with this provision is a ground for revocation of licence.³⁸

However, this begs the question what does a minimum paid-up share capital means? A minimum paid-up share capital refers to the portion of the issued share for which payment has been made by the shareholders.³⁹ A Paid-up share capital, also known as paid-in capital or issued and paid-up capital, refers to the amount of money that shareholders have invested in a company by purchasing its shares. It represents the total amount of capital that has been paid in by shareholders to acquire shares of the company.

(d) Shareholder's Voting Right to be Proportional to Shareholding

Shareholders of a bank are those registered by a company as legal owners of shares of the share capital of the company. Generally, they possess certain rights and powers, the shareholders have the right to vote and similarly have the powers to appoint or remove directors, appoint auditors and determine their remuneration, alter company's share capital, change company's name etc.

³⁵ S. 7 (7) BOFIA 2020

³⁶ S. 7 (3) BOFIA 2020

³⁷S. 9(1) BOFIA 2020.

³⁸S. 9(2) BOFIA 2020.

³⁹accessed from <<https://pavestoneslegal.com/share-capita;-requirement-for-companies-with-foreign-participation-in-Nigeria>> on 22ndfebruary, 2024 .

In relation to the voting right of shareholders, the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) 2020 provides that any member holding shares in the company conferring a right to vote may demand for a poll at any general meeting"⁴⁰ The BOFIA on the other hand, prescribed that such right must be proportionate to the individual contribution to the paid up share capital of the bank.⁴¹ The basic rule is 'one share one vote' no company is allowed to authorize the issue of shares which has more than one vote except the Articles and Memorandum of Association provides a shareholder can have more than one vote per share in certain circumstances. The CAMA in relation to this, stated that notwithstanding anything to the contrary in terms of the articles, include the right to attend any general meeting of the company and vote at such meeting, the rights and liabilities attached to shares of a company or any class thereof shall be dependent on terms of issue or the company's articles.⁴²

Where a shareholder is deprived of his right, he is entitled to enforce or take legal action to claim his right in *Pender v. Lushington*⁴³ the plaintiff, a shareholder whose vote was not recorded by the chairman causing him to lose the resolution proposed by him sued to have his vote recorded and it was held that he was entitled to have his vote recorded.⁴⁴

(e) Minimum Holding of Cash Reserves, Specified Liquid Assets, Special Deposits and Stabilisation Securities

The Act states that every bank shall maintain with the Bank, Cash reserves, and special deposits or any non-interest banking instruments as may be approved by the Bank and hold specified liquid assets or other securities, as the case may be, not less in amount as may be prescribed by the Bank by virtue of section 45 of the Central Bank Act⁴⁵

The minimum cash reserve is a specified proportion of reserves that a bank is mandated to hold in its vault or with the Central Bank and cannot be given out as loans

⁴⁰ S. 248 (1)(d) CAMA 2020

⁴¹S.10 BOFIA 2020

⁴² S. 138 CAMA 2020

⁴³(1877) 6 ChD 70.

⁴⁴Nnyeruka J.L, Amadi F.C &ChidiHalliday, 'Shareholders' Rights & Obligations Under The Companies And Allied Matters Act' Accessed from<<https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Halliday-Chidi/publication/332291667>> on 22nd July 2024.

⁴⁵S. 14 (1) BOFIA 2020

or used for investments. It is usually a proportion of the deposit liabilities of commercial banks.⁴⁶ In other words, it implies the amount of cash that banks must hold in reserve to ensure that it is able to meet its liabilities in case of sudden withdrawals and to be able to meet customers' immediate demands.

The Special deposit refers to the deposits that commercial banks may be asked to hold with the central Bank in addition to those that they may hold as part of their cash reserves. While a liquid asset is defined as the obligation of commercial banks to maintain a predetermined percentage of total deposits and certain other liabilities in the form of liquid assets. The eligible range of assets varies, but usually includes cash, deposits with the central bank, correspondent accounts, and government securities.⁴⁷ All these are monetary policy tools used by the CBN to limit the circulation of money or supply in the economy, as banks liquidity drops.

Important to note that the special deposits do not count as liquid assets as such are not part of the liquid assets ratio. However, it is designed to bring pressure on the banks' liquid assets as a means of restricting advances.

(f) Minimum Capital Ratio

The capital ratio also known as Capital Adequacy Ratio refers to the percentage of banks capital to its risk-weighted assets⁴⁸ or the amount of capital a bank or other financial institution has to have as required by its financial regulator.⁴⁹

The BOFI Act 2020 provides that a bank shall maintain at all times minimum capital ratio (capital funds unimpaired by losses) as may be specified by the Bank.⁵⁰ In the same vein, the banks are required to maintain a minimum regulatory capital adequacy ratio of 10/15% on an ongoing basis.

4.0 Challenges of the Industry/Licence

4.1. Challenges of Fraud, Insecurity and Manpower

⁴⁶ See CBN, Monetary Policy Glance

⁴⁷See Anne M.G, Jean-Claude N. and Lorena M.Z, 'Liquid Asset Requirement: Role and Reform accessed from <<https://www.>> on 23rd February 2024

⁴⁸. Cambridge Online Dictionary, accessed from <<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/capital-ratio>> on 23 February 2025.

⁴⁹Wikipedia, accessed from <<en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/capital-requirement>> on 23rd February 2025

⁵⁰ S. 13(1) BOFIA 2020

So many challenges exist and are affecting the smooth running of the Nigerian banking industry. The challenges of Fraud, insecurity and manpower pose significant threat to the stability and integrity of the industry. In recent times, fraudulent practices have been on the increase, it has eaten deep into the banking industry as well as the entire economics in Nigeria. Fraud is an intentional act by one or more individuals among management, employees or third parties which results in a misrepresentation of financial statement. It's devastating effect manifests itself in the deteriorating balance sheet of banks as well as in economic backwardness.⁵¹

Secondly, the challenge of insecurity across the country has posed a tremendous danger to the operations and business models of the banking institutions. Virtually all the six geo-political zones have security issues. The Niger Delta militants in the South-South region, there is Boko Haram insurgency in the North-East, banditry in the North- West region, kidnappings and killings in the North-Central. There are communal conflicts, armed attacks, farmers-herders' conflicts, and assassinations in the South – East, and the South West is having challenges of violent attacks, kidnappings, killings, herdsman invasion on private farmlands.⁵² This has led to the destruction of lives and properties, hindered business activities, discouraged local and foreign investors, increased government expenditure on security, all of these stifle and retard Nigeria's socio-economic development.⁵³

The problem of insecurity has negatively affected the Nigerian banking industry. Like all other social and economic activities, the banks suffer from security challenges in any environment directly and indirectly resulting into bad loans, reduction of business transactions, increase in loan defaults, decrease in interest incomes and earnings and job cuts. The increasing rate of insecurity and fraud in the banking system, if not addressed might pose serious threats to the stability and the survival of individual banks and the performance of the industry as a whole.

⁵¹Badejo BA, Okuneye BA, Taiwo MR, 'Fraud Detection in the Banking System in Nigeria Challenges and Prospects', *Journal of Economics and Business*, Volume 2, No. 3, September - December 2017 accessed from www.researchgate.net/publication/322468595 on 5 January 2025.

⁵²Ilemobayo, AS, Adelowontan, M O, Itemeh, G G, 'Impact of Security Challenges on Bank Performance in Nigeria' *The International Journal Of Business & Management*, Vol 10 Issue 3 DOI No.: 10.24940/theijbm/2022/v10/i3/BM2203-001 March, 2022 accessed from on 6 January 2025

⁵³ Ibid

Another daunting challenge is manpower or human resources management, the human resources is seen as more potent and effective weapon in the banking industry. Of course, if a country desires to attain growth and development on sustainable basis then the task of creating adequate human and institutional capacity must be made a primary concern. This is necessary because when there is the absence of human capital nothing enduring takes place in the organization. According to the NDIC 1996 Annual Reports, Forty-Seven (47) Commercial banks were declared technically distressed between 1994/1996 in Nigeria. Also, out of 231 Community Banks examined by the NDIC in 1996, 200 of them were adjudged technically distressed. There is compelling body of evidence to show that Manpower problems contributed to the collapse of banks in Nigeria in the 1990s. Manpower development is seen as a deliberate and systematic effort to build, strengthen and nurture the skills required for the performance of specific tasks. Such skills provide the recipient with highly specialized tools for the objective investigation of the facts pertaining to a specific problem or problems. Banks should pay attention to Manpower development vis-à-vis worker education, experience and technical competence.⁵⁴

4.2. Challenges in Adhering to the Strict Requirements for Grant of Licence

The BOFIA 2020 enumerates certain requirements for obtaining a banking licence. *These requirements are laced with enormous difficulty and hardship.* For instance, the Act provides that an applicant must deposit the minimum paid up share capital with the CBN before license will be issued and upon fulfilling such condition within such period prescribed by the Bank, the CBN with the approval of the board issue licence.⁵⁵ Failure to comply with this provision is a ground for refusal to issue licence.

Again, the power of the CBN to “vary or revoke any condition subject to which a licence was granted or to impose fresh or additional conditions to the grant of a licence”.⁵⁶ Whenever such variation is done, it applies as though the varied condition was

⁵⁴ John N.N.U, 'Manpower Challenges in the Banking Sector a Nigerian Perspective' accessed from <<http://ssrn.com/abstract=2566838>> on 1st January 2025.

⁵⁵ S. 3(2) BOFIA 2020

⁵⁶ S. 5 (1) and (2) BOFIA 2020

applicable at the grant of licence. The failure to adhere to this condition will inevitably lead to a revocation.⁵⁷

In May 2023, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) through its Governor, by a notice published in the official gazette of the Federal Government, revoked the operating licenses of about one hundred and seventy-nine (179) Microfinance Banks (“MFBs”), three (3) Finance Companies and four (4) Primary Mortgage Banks (“PMBs”) for failure to fulfill or comply with the conditions subject to which their licenses were granted; or failed to comply with the obligations imposed upon them by the Central Bank of Nigeria in accordance with the provisions of Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act 2020⁵⁸. Even though, revocation of a banking licence does not lead to the death of a bank, however, it is important to highlight that gaining public trust again is a daunting task that is almost impossible.

4.3. Concentration of Licence Power in the Hands of the Governor

The BOFIA 2020 bestows on the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria the unfettered and unquestionable discretion to grant or not to grant this licence. The BOFIA states that the CBN governor needs not give reason for his revocation, but this particular power is against the principle of fair hearing as enshrined under the constitution.⁵⁹Therefore, it is feared that the Governor may misuse such power given to him and arbitrarily revoke licenses.

It is a trite principle of law that where a case or an allegation is made against a legal person, that such person should be given the opportunity to present his/her defence. The essence of this position is so that the party may by its defence, present tangible evidence/facts justifying its position or presenting better evidence to portray true position of things as doing otherwise will amount to a breach of right to fair hearing. See the case of *Okafor & Ors v Okafor & Ors*.⁶⁰ The right to being heard fairly is so

⁵⁷ S. 12 (a) BOFIA 2020

⁵⁸Simon Ngwu, The Arbitrary Powers of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to revoke the operating licenses of Banks and Financial Institutions in Nigeria. Accessed from <<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/arbitrary-powers-central-bank-nigeria-cbn-revoke-operating-simon-ngwu-nmlcf>> on 6 January 2024.

⁵⁹Section 36 (5) Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999 as amended 2011.

⁶⁰(2016) LPELR-42092(CA)

fundamental and should not be toyed with under any guise. As a matter of both fact and law, it is the whole essence of the equitable maxim: *audi alteram partem*.⁶¹

5.0 Findings of the Study

- (a) The Act put in more stringent requirements for the grant of licence. Although, those stringent requirements were meant to protect the integrity of the industry, notwithstanding, it hinders the fast growth of the industry.
- (b) That too much power resides in the hands of the CBN Governor in that, he reserves the absolute powers to either grants or otherwise refuse to grant licence. His decision is final and cannot be questioned in that regards.
- (c) In action challenging such revocation, no restorative order shall be granted against the Bank or the Governor in any action, suit or proceedings in relation to the revocation of a license by the Bank under the Act, and the remedy of any claimant or applicant against the Bank or the Governor in any such action, suit or proceedings is limited to monetary compensation not exceeding the equivalent of the value of the paid-up capital of the bank at the time of the revocation of its license.⁶²

6.0 Recommendations

- (a) It is recommended that the provision of section 3 which enumerates the requirements for in applying for licence be revised so as to ameliorate the hardship in obtaining a banking licence
- (b) It is recommended that the power vested in the CBN Governor to either grant or reject license application without giving any reason be revised as it is in direct conflict with Constitution.
- (c) The provision that the only remedy available for wrongful revocation is monetary compensation needs to be looked into. This would imply that any bank can lose its licence on the slightest excuse without a chance of regaining it.

7.0 Conclusion

⁶¹ Ibid

⁶² Simon N, 'The Arbitrary Powers of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to revoke the operating licenses of Banks and Financial Institutions in Nigeria' accessed from on

BOFIA 2020 provides a stronger and more comprehensive legal framework for banking industry activities in Nigeria and has set out steps in acquiring licenses to operate a bank in Nigeria authorizing the Central Bank of Nigeria to issue such licences. The licence is the pillar upon which the entire banking business rest. However, like other legislations, BOFIA 2020 is not without shortfalls, the requirements for obtaining a banking licence are daunting, centralization of powers in the Central Bank is yet another challenge and as such this paper recommends a review so as to ameliorate these overreaching hardships.